

Synthesis of certain Sulphonamides and Aminopyranoquinoline Derivatives from 4-Hydroxyquinoline with Biological Interest

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Various sulphonamides derivatives (3a-d) have been synthesised by the pyridine ring opening of 4-hydroxyquinoline monoxime (2a-d), and screened for their antibacterial activity. Furthermore, the reactivity of 4-hydroxyquinoline (1) towards different activated nitriles has been studied.

DURING the course of our study on nucleophilic cleavage reactions of the pyridine ring we found that 2-benzylpyridine in alkaline medium rearranged to give 2-aminobiphenyls¹. Although, a few reactions of opening the pyridine ring in the quinoline compounds have appeared in the literature² no studies have been carried out on the 4-hydroxyquinoline derivatives. Therefore, we were interested in studying the Beckmann rearrangement of the carbostyrile monoxime of the type 2. It had been observed³ that α -nitroso- β -naphthol yields *o*-cyanocinnamoyl chloride when treated with benzene sulphonyl chloride in pyridine. Indandione monoxime⁴ appears to yield carboxyphenyl acetone nitrile under similar conditions, while 5-nitroso-6-hydroxyquinoline yields (3-cyanopyridyl-2)acrylic acid⁵. We report here our observations on the reaction of the carbostyrile monoxime (2a-d) (which contains both the hydroxyl and nitroso groups in the pyridine ring) with benzene sulphonyl chloride.

The carbostyrile derivatives (1a-d) were prepared from aniline (or its derivatives), malonic acid and phosphorous oxychloride in presence of naphthalene (suitable for eliminating the formation of contaminating pyranocarbostyriles)⁶. The intermediates carbostyrile monoximes (2a-d) were obtained by the nitrosation of 1a-d with sodium nitrite in hydrochloric acid.

We now wish to report the extension of our original investigation to the use of pyridine compounds and the utilisation of the reaction as a route for obtaining new *N*-benzenesulphonyl compounds of interesting antibacterial activity. The main difference in the two reaction sequences is our choice of the pyridine compounds as starting materials and interesting solvent effect upon the course of rearrangement. Therefore, when the monoxime compounds (2a-d) were treated with benzene sulphonyl chloride, the normal rearrangement products anthranilic acid derivatives were not obtained. Instead, the cleavage of pyridine ring occurred with the formation of *N*-benzenesulphonyl derivatives (3a-d).

The rearrangement of the monoxime compounds (2a-d) to *N*-benzenesulphonyl derivatives (3a-d) may occur according to the mechanism presented in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

We then investigated the reactivity of 4-hydroxyquinoline (1) towards activated nitrile compounds⁸. Thus, it has been found that 1b undergoes reaction with ethyl cyanoacetate to give the aminopyranoquinoline (4). The formation of such compound is assumed to proceed via the loss of ethanol to yield acyclic compound which cyclises via addition of the ring carbonyl to the cyano group. Similarly, 1b undergoes reaction with acrylonitrile to yield the pyranoquinoline (5), whose formation is assumed to proceed via initial Michael addition of 1 to the activated double bond of acrylonitrile to yield acrylic Michael adduct. The latter then cyclises via addition of the ring carbonyl to cyano group to give compound 5 (Scheme 2).

In contrast to the behaviour of ethyl cyanoacetate, phenacyl cyanide reacts with 1b to yield a condensation product for which structures 6 or 7 were suggested, and the latter was established as the correct one, ν_{\max} 2 200 cm^{-1} (CN). Similarly, 1b was condensed with phenacyl thiocyanate to give the condensation product⁹. Structures of all compounds were inferred from elemental analysis and spectral evidence.

Scheme 2

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1-8*

Compd.* no.	M.p. °C	λ_{max} (log ϵ)	ν_{max} cm^{-1}	δ
1a	300 ^a	226(4.9), 282(3.6), 300(3.8)		
1b	300	223(4.9), 2.80(3.6), 320		1.9 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.5 (1H, s, OH), 6.8-7.4 (4H, m, ArH+C ₅ -H), 9.7 (1H, s, NH)
1c	330	225(4.8), 276(3.6), 324	3 400-3 200 (OH, NH), 1 640 (amide CO), 600-500 (C-Br)	6.5 (1H, s, OH), 6.8-7.5 (4H, m, $3 \times \text{ArH} + \text{C}_5\text{-H}$), 9.8 (1H, s, NH)
1d	330	224(4.8), 279 (3.6), 322(3.8)	3 400-3 200 (OH, NH), 1 640 (CO), 800-600 (C-Cl)	
2a	200 ^b	240(4.0), 250(4.2), 340		
2b	190	240(4.0), 254(4.2), 340(4.1)	3 200 (NH), 1 680 (CO), 1 660 (C=N oxime), 1 640 (CO), 3 400 (OH)	1.9 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.7 (1H, s, OH), 6.9-7.7 (3H, m, ArH), 9.4 (1H, s, NH)
2c	145	241(4.1), 254(4.2), 341		6.7 (1H, s, OH), 6.9-7.6 (3H, m, ArH), 9.5 (1H, s, NH)
2d	163	241(4.2), 250(4.2), 240(4.2)		
3a	208	330(4.2)		
3b	130	328(4.2)	1 720 (CO), 1 350-1 325, 1 160-1 155 (-HNSO ₃ -)	1.8 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.7-7.8 (3H, m, ArH), 11.0 (1H, s, NH)
3c	243	327(4.2)	1 715 (CO), 1 350-1 325, 1 160-1 155 (-HNSO ₃ -), 600-500 (C-Br)	
3d	130	330(4.2)		
4	300	—	3 500-3 200 (NH ₂ +NH), 1 700 (pyrane CO), 1 680 (CO)	1.9 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.0 (2H, s, br, NH ₂), 6.8-7.5 (4H, m, $3 \times \text{ArH} + \text{CH}$), 9.5 (1H, s, NH)
5	320	—	3 100-2 900 ($\text{CH}_2 + \text{CH}_2$), 1 680 (CO), 1 100 (C-O-C)	1.8 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.5-5.0 (3H, m, aliphatic CH_2 and pyrone NH ₂), 7.8-8.0 (5H, m, $3 \times \text{ArH}$ and amide NH ₂)
7	220	—	2 200 (CN), 1 680, 1 660, 1 640 (CO, C=C, CO)	1.9 (1H, s, CH_3), 2.5 (2H, s, CH_2), 6.8-7.7 (3H, m, ArH), 9.7 (1H, s, NH)
8	130	—	—	—

*Ref. 7. ^bRef. 8.

N-Benzenesulphonyl derivatives (3) at concentration 0.5 mg, were found to have a good antibacterial activity specially on the growth of *E. coli* (zone of inhibition 34–44 mm) and *S. aureus* (28–35 mm) in comparison to the reference drugs chloramphenicol (22, 23 mm) and kanamycin (32, 31 mm respectively).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc in benzene. ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆; 60 MHz) were determined using TMS as internal standard on a Varian 360 EM spectrometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Pye-Unicam S.P. 1100 spectrophotometer and uv spectra (ethanol) on a Perkin-Elmer 402 spectrophotometer.

4-Hydroxycarbostryles (1a–d). *General procedure:* A mixture of aniline (0.1 mol), malonic acid (0.18 mol), phosphorous oxychloride (36 g) and naphthalene (15 g) was heated on a water-bath for 0.5 h. The mixture was then diluted with water, basified by sodium hydroxide to pH 9, filtered and the filtrate acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid to pH 2–3. The resulting solid was crystallised from acetic acid to give compounds 1a–d (Table 1).

3-Nitroso-4-hydroxycarbostryle (2a–d). *General procedure:* To a cold solution (2–0°) of 1a–d (0.01 mol), sodium hydroxide (0.018 mol) in water (80 ml) and sodium nitrite (0.15 mol), was added dilute HCl (9 ml) within 20 min. The mixture was then stirred for 0.5 h and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Rearrangement products (3a–d). *General procedure:* A mixture of 2 (0.015 mol) and benzenesulphonyl chloride (0.018 mol) in acetone (50 ml) was heated with stirring for 0.5 h. A solution of NaOH (2g) in water (30 ml) was added to it with continuous heating for further 0.5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, neutralised with 10% HCl, acetone was evaporated out and the residual solution was acidified with dilute HCl. The solid obtained was boiled in water (20 ml) containing sodium bicarbonate (2 g) and charcoal (1 g), filtered and the filtrate acidified by 10% HCl. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol.

Reaction of compound 1b with activated nitriles. *General procedure:* All the reactions described in this paper were easy to carry out. Heating under reflux of equimolar amounts of the reactants in ethanol for 8–10 h with a catalytic amount of piperidine or triethylamine (or in pyridine as solvent in the case of 7 and 8), is adequate to ensure complete reaction (Table 1)).

Antibacterial susceptibility assay: The *N*-benzenesulphonyl derivatives (3a–d) were tested against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Sterptococcus viridans*, *Mycobacterium smegmatis*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherishia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Candida albicans* as yeast. The antibacterial activity of each compound at 500, 1000 µg per test as well as 30 µg for therapeutic agents was performed by the agar cup gradient technique as described earlier. All plates were run in triplicates and incubated for 48 h at 37°.

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